

TO STUDY THE KINETICS AND MECHANISM OF UNCATALYSED LIGAND SUBSTITUTION REACTION BETWEEN HEXACYANOFERRATE (II) AND DPQ

Dr. Anupma Singh

Asst. Prof. (DDU Government PG College, Sitapur)

ABSTRACT

The kinetics and mechanism of uncatalysed substitution of co-ordinated cyanide in hexacyanoferrate (II) by a nitrogen donor heterocyclic ligand, dpqanthroline at 547nm (λ max of a intense green coloured compound $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{dpq}]^{3-}$ as a function of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ and $[\text{dpq}]$ under the conditions, $\text{pH} = 2.5 \pm 0.02$, temperature = $25.0 \pm 0.10^\circ\text{C}$, ionic strength (I) = 0.05 M(KNO_3). The reaction is a first order each in $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ and $[\text{Dpq}]$ at low $[\text{dpq}]$ concentration. The rate of the reaction is determined from the slopes of absorbances versus time plots. As $[\text{dpq}]$ increases the rate of the reaction increases, passes through a maximum and then falls, suggesting that the course of the reaction is different at low $[\text{dpq}]$ and high $[\text{dpq}]$. The effect of temperature and pH on the initial rate have also been explained and studied. The repetitive spectral scans is also provided as an evidence for exchange of cyanide ions by $[\text{dpq}]$ in $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$. Activation parameters have also been evaluated and provided in support of the proposed mechanistic scheme. The composition of the complex was established as 1:1 by the mole ratio method.

Keywords: dpq, hexacyanoferrate, ligand substitution, rate of reaction

INTRODUCTION

Dipyrido[3,2-d:2',3'-f]quinoxaline (dpq) (Scheme 1) is a heterocyclic organic compound. As a bidentate ligand in co-ordination chemistry, it forms strong complexes with most metal ions. It is used in transition metal chemistry for determination of metals, as an indicator for alkyl lithium reagents. It is used in metallocene industry and co-ordination of organometallic complexes.

dpq

Dipyrido[3,2-d:2',3'-f]quinoxaline (dpq)

Scheme 1

Complexes of the type $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{INH}^{3-}]$ [1] and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{phen}]^{3-}$ [2] have been obtained either through photochemical aquation of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ or by Hg^{+2} assisted complexes of the type $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{L}$ ($\text{L} = \text{N}_3^-$, PhNO , amines) have been prepared by substitution in pentacyano amino ferrate (II) or mercury catalysed substitution in hexacyanoferrate (II) molecular complexes of Pyrazine (Pz) and $[\text{Ru}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ having molecular formula $[\text{Ru}(\text{CN})_5\text{Pz}]^{3-}$ [7] and N-methyl Pyrazine and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ [8] have been reported. The thermal decomposition of hexacyanoferrate (II) ion is a slow reversible process according to equation

1. The pentacyanoaquo complex produced has been reported [9] to react with aromatic nitroso compounds giving intensely coloured products.

There is limited information on the kinetics and mechanism concerning substitution in hexacyanoferrate (II) [10-13]. Exchange of labelled cyanide between $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ and free cyanide is extremely slow, but under U.V. light reversible aquation takes place [14]. Most of the substituted cyano complexes of Iron (II) are metal assisted dissociation of hexacyanoferrate (II) [11,15] followed by reaction with the incoming ligand. Many complexes of the pentacyano (ligand.) ferrate (II) type have been prepared by substitution in pentacyano (amino) ferrate (II) or by metal catalysed substitution in hexacyanoferrate (II) [2,8,11,12,16-21]

In accordance with our earlier investigation of the reaction of dpqyl hydrazine [1] and pyrazine [7] with hexacyanoferrate (II), Dipyrido (dpq) has also been shown to react with $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ according to Eqns.1-3. The uncatalysed reaction takes about 24 hours to attain maximum absorbance.

The stoichiometry of the complex has been established as 1:1 by the mole ratio [22] and slope method [23].

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents

Double distilled water was used throughout to prepare all solutions. All the chemicals used in this study were of analytical reagent grade. The solution of $\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R.E. Merck, Germany) was prepared by weighing a desired amount and kept in dark in coloured bottles to prevent photochemical dissociation. The fresh solutions of Dipyrido (S.D. Fine Chemicals) was prepared in double distilled water everyday before starting the kinetic run. KNO_3 (A.R. Glaxo) was used to maintain ionic strength in reaction medium. The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted to a desired value using buffer solutions prepared by adding NaOH or HCl to potassium hydrogen phthalate (A.R. Qualigens Fine chemicals) as reported in the literature [24].

Apparatus

All the reactant solutions were equilibrated at 25°C by keeping them inside environmental chamber in order to maintain the desired temperature within the accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$. Genesis model No. 10UV was used to record the spectra of the reaction. The pH measurements were made on a digital pH meter of Sio-global pH meter.

Procedure

After equilibrating the reactants, 2 ml of each reactant was mixed in the sequence, dpq and buffer. The reaction was finally started by adding 2 ml of hexacyanoferrate (II) to the above mixture. This reaction mixture was shaken thoroughly and quickly transferred to a 10 mm cuvette in the temperature controlled cell compartment of the spectrophotometer. The progress of the reaction was subsequently followed by monitoring the increase in absorbance at 547 n.m. due to formation of the product $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{dpq}]^{3-}$ (Fig.1)

Figure 1: A repetitive Spectral Scan of the reaction mixture During the kinetic run

Under conditions: $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-} = 5.5 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$, $[\text{dpq}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$, $\text{pH} = 2.5 \pm 0.02$, $\text{Temp.} = 25 \text{ C}$, $I = 0.05\text{M}$ (KNO_3)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$

Effect of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ on the initial rate of uncatalysed reaction between $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ and dpq was studied taking $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ $1.0 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$ to $8.0 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$. The reaction was found to exhibit first order behavior in $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ in the concentration range studied. The plot of initial rate (V_i) versus $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ in a straight line as shown in Fig. 2 ($r^2=0.995$, $s_d=0.223$).

Fig. 2. Plot of initial rate of the uncatalysed ligand exchange reaction versus $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$

Under Conditions: $[\text{dpq}] = 3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $\text{pH} = 2.5 \pm 0.02$, $\text{Temp.} = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$, $I = 0.03 \text{ M}(\text{KNO}_3)$.

Effect of [dpq]

The effect of [dpq] on the initial rate for uncatalysed ligand substitution reaction between $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ and [dpq] was studied by varying Dipyrido concentration from $0.4 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$ to $14.0 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$. The plot of initial rate versus [dpq] is shown in Figure 3. It is seen that the initial rate increases with increasing the concentration of dpqanthroline. It rises till $8.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ and remains constant between $9.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ to $12.5 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$ and then starts declining at further increase in [dpq].

Fig. 3. Varying effect of [Dpq] on initial rate of unanalyzed ligand exchange Reaction between $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ and [dpq]

Under Conditions: $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-} = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $\text{pH} = 2.5 \pm 0.02$, $\text{Temp.} = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$, $I = 0.03 \text{ M}$ (KNO_3).

Effect of pH on initial rate

The dependence of initial rate on pH in co-ordinated cyanide substitution from $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ by [dpq] was studied in the pH range 1.5-7.0. In the beginning i.e. pH range 1.5-3.0 the rate increases and at still higher pH the rate decreases. This behaviour shows the existence of protonated and deprotonated forms of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ and [dpq], all having different reactivities. From species distribution of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ shown in Fig.4, it can be seen that in the lower pH range there exist mono, di, tri and tetra protonated species of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$. The initial increase in the rate between pH 1.5 – 3.0 is due to inter conversions of highly protonated forms of hexacyanoferrate (II) into lower protonated forms.

Figure 4. Species distribution of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ as a function of pH.

$\text{E} = [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, $\text{B} = \text{H}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$, $\text{C} = \text{H}_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{2-}$, $\text{D} = \text{H}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{-}$ and $\text{A} = \text{H}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$

The rate law for the pH range 3.0-7.0 can be expressed according to Eqn. (4) where deprotonated forms of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ and $[\text{Dpq}]$, $[\text{DpqH}]^+$ or both are prominent reacting species.

$$\text{Rate} = k_f [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}]_T [\text{dpq}] \quad 4$$

Here subscript 'T' refers to the total concentrations of the reacting species and k_f ($k_f = \text{Rate} / [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}] [\text{dpq}]$) in the forward bimolecular rate constant. In the above mentioned pH region $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}]$ exists predominantly in deprotonated form and dpqanthroline exists as Dpq and DpqH^+

Therefore equation (4) can be transformed to Eqn(5)

$$\text{Rate} = \{k_{\text{dpq}} + k_{\text{dpqH}^+} K_{\text{dpqH}^+} [\text{H}^+]\} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}]_T [\text{dpq}]_f \quad 5$$

From Eqn. (4) and (5) we get

$$k_f \frac{([\text{dpq}]_T)}{[\text{dpq}]_f} = k_{\text{dpq}} + k_{\text{dpqH}^+} + K_{\text{dpqH}^+} [\text{H}^+] \quad 6$$

$$\frac{([\text{dpq}]_T)}{[\text{dpq}]_f} = 1 + K_{\text{dpqH}^+} [\text{H}^+]$$

Here, subscript 'f' denotes the concentration of dpqanthroline in the unprotonated form, k_{dpq} , k_{dpqH^+} and K_{dpqH^+} refers to the rate constants due to reactions of dpq and dpqH⁺ and protonation constant of dpq respectively. The plot of the left hand side of Eqn. (6) versus $[\text{H}^+]$ yields a straight line (Fig. 5). $r^2 \approx 0.9952$ and its slope and intercept give the value of $k_{\text{dpqH}^+} = 47.8 \pm 5.50 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ L s}^{-1}$ and $k_{\text{Dpq}} = 68.9 \pm 5.12 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ L s}^{-1}$. The values resolved rate constants are in fairly good agreement with the experimentally observed values at high and low pH values respectively.

Figure 5. Resolution of rate constants for the reaction of $[\text{dpq}]$ and $[\text{dpqH}]^+$ with $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$

Effect of Temperature on Initial rate

The effect of temperature on the initial rate of the uncatalysed reaction between hexacyanoferrate (II) and dpqanthroline was studied at different temperatures ranging from 25 - 45°C and the activation parameters were calculated by Arrhenius and Eyring equations and are given in Table below .

Activation Parameter for the uncatalysed replacement of CN⁻ in Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻

Activation Parameter	Value
ΔE _a	65.92 ± 2.5 KJmol ⁻¹
Δ H [‡]	64.32 ± 2.9 KJmol ⁻¹
Δ S [#]	-38.99 ± 5.8 KJmol ⁻¹

Under conditions : Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻ = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M , [dpq] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ M , pH = 2.5 ± 0.02, temp .25 ± 0.1 °C and I = 0.03 M (KNO₃)

Higher temperatures were avoided due to decomposition of the complex [Fe (CN)₅ dpq]³⁻. The evaluated activation parameters show the dissociation type mechanism. The high value of E_a shows the rupture of metal ligand bond, which supports the proposed mechanism.

Effect of Ionic strength

The effect of ionic strength on the rate of the uncatalysed reaction between [Fe (CN)₆]⁴⁻ and [dpq] was studied in the range 0.01-0.03 M using KNO₃. The initial rate of the reaction was found to decrease with increase in ionic strength of the medium that indicates a negative salt effect. The observed rate dependence on both the reactants, temperature, pH and ionic strength allowed us to propose the following mechanism (Scheme 2).

[A]

k₃(slow)

Scheme 2

The rate law based on the above scheme can be expressed by Eqn. (7)

$$d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{dpq}]/dt = k_3[\text{A}^\ddagger] \quad 7$$

If k₂ >> k₃, the formation of [A][‡] is due to a fast equilibrium and for the condition where [Fe (CN)₅H₂O]³⁻ < [dpq], the equilibrium concentration of activated complex [A][‡] (or ion pair) is evaluated by using the following algebraic manipulation and finally given by Eqn. (8)

$$\text{Or} \quad [\text{A}^\ddagger] = [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{3-}] - ([\text{A}^\ddagger])/(k_2[\text{dpq}])$$

Where
$$K_2 = [A^\ddagger]/[Fe(CN)_5H_2O^{3-}]_f [dpq]$$

and 'f' refer to the free concentration of $[Fe(CN)_5H_2O]^{3-}$

Or
$$[A^\ddagger] = 1 + 1/K_2[dpq] = [Fe(CN)_5H_2O^{3-}]$$

Or
$$[A^\ddagger](1 + K_2[dpq]) = K_2[Fe(CN)_5H_2O^{3-}][dpq]$$

Or
$$[A^\ddagger] = \frac{K_2[Fe(CN)_5H_2O^{3-}][dpq]}{1 + K_2[dpq]}$$

Applying steady state approximation to the intermediate $[Fe(CN)_5H_2O]^{3-}$, one gets

$$[Fe(CN)_5H_2O^{3-}] = \frac{k_1(1 + K_2[dpq])[Fe(CN)_5][H_2O]}{K_1(1 + K_2[dpq])[CN^-] + k_2K_2[dpq]^2}$$

9

Substituting Eqn. (9) in Eqn. (8) we get Eqn.10

$$[A^\ddagger] = \frac{k_1K_2[dpq][Fe(CN)_6^{4-}][H_2O]}{k_{-1}[CN^-](1 + K_2[dpq])[CN^-] + k_2K_2[dpq]^2}$$

10

Considering Eqns. (9) and (10), the rate law given is expressed as Eqn. (11)

$$d[Fe(CN)_5dpq]^{3-}/dt = \frac{k_3 k_1 K_2 [dpq] [Fe(CN)_6^{4-}] [H_2O]}{k_{-1}[CN^-](1 + K_2[dpq])[CN^-] + k_2K_2[dpq]^2}$$

11

If in Eqn. (11) k_2 and k_{-1} are comparable (both are fast), the following two conditions may exist.

(i) At low $[Dpq]$, $k_{-1}[CN^-] > k_2[Dpq]$.

The second term of denominator in Eqn. (11) is greater than the third term and second term comprises multiple and small concentration terms. Thus, both can be neglected in comparison to $k_{-1}[CN^-]$. Therefore, Eqn. (11) is reduced to Eqn. (12).

$$d[Fe(CN)_5dpq]^{3-}/dt = \frac{k_3 k_1 K_2 [dpq] [Fe(CN)_6^{4-}] [H_2O]}{k_{-1}[CN^-]}$$

12

Eqn. (12) shows an increase in rate with increase in $[dpq]$

(ii) At high $[dpq]$, $k_2[dpq] \gg k_{-1}[CN^-]$.

This implies that the third term in the denominator in Eqn. (11) is greater than the first and second terms and consequently the rate law can be expressed by Eqn. (13)

$$d[Fe(CN)_5dpq]^{3-}/dt = \frac{k_3 k_1 [Fe(CN)_6^{4-}] [H_2O]}{k_2[dpq]}$$

13

In terms of Eqn. (13), we expect a decrease in the rate of formation of product with Finally, the repetitive spectral scan (Fig. 5) of the uncatalysed substitution reaction between $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ and $[dpq]$ have been recorded at definite times in the wavelength range 455 to 655 nm under

the specified reaction conditions in order to understand the nature of the product formed during the course of the reaction and provide better understanding of the proposed mechanism. The repetitive spectral scan (Fig.5) shows that a peak continuously grows with time at 547 nm. This is attributed to the formation of the final product, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{dpq}]^{3-}$ during the course of the reaction. The mole ratio studies performed by us show the formation of a 1:1 complex, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{dpq}]^{3-}$ as the final product of the reaction, as shown by other researchers [25].

REFERENCES

1. Naik, Radhey Mohan, Tiwari, R.K., Yadav, S.B.S., Singh, P.K., Agarwal, A., 2009, *Progress in Reaction Kinetics and Mechanism*, Vol. 34, pp.211.
 2. Naik R.K., Tiwari R.K., Singh P.K., Verma A.K., 2007, *Inorganic Reaction Mechanism*, Vol.6, pp.217.
 3. Legros, J., 1964, *J Chem Phys.*, Vol. 61, pp.217.
 4. Kenney, D.J., Flynn, T.P., Calline, J.B., 1965, *J Inorg Nucl Chem.*, Vol.20, 75.
 5. Dupleseis J., Legros J, Emischwiller G., 1971, *Compt. Rend.*, Vol.273, pp.452.
 6. Asperger S., Pavlovic D., 1955, *J Chem Soc.*, pp.1449.
 7. Naik Radhey M., Verma Amit K., Agarwal Abhivav., Asthana Abhas., 2009, *Transition Metal Chem.*, Vol. 34, pp.209.
 8. Prasad Surendra., 2003, *Transition Met Chem.*, Vol. 28, pp.1.
 9. Bandisch., 1929, *Ber.*, Vol. 62, pp.2706.
 10. Zmikia, Cvitila A., Pavloic D., Murati D., Reynolds I., As perger, S. 1973, *J., Chem Soc Dalton Trans.*, pp.1284.
 11. Feng Y.L., Narasaki (II), Tian L.C., Wu S.M., Chen, (II) Y., 1999, *Anal Sci.*, Vol.15, pp. 915.
 12. Prasad S., Nigam P.C., 1989, *Indian J Enviv Protec.*, Vol.9, pp.113.
 13. Phull M., Nigam P.C., 1981, *Talanta.*, Vol.28, pp.519.
 14. Kuhn D.D., Young T.C., 2005, *Chemosphere.*, Vol.60, pp.1222.
 15. Sicilia D., Rubio S., Perez-Bendito D., 1991, *Talanta* ., Vol.38, pp. 1147.
 16. Qin W., Guohua C., Jinhu V., Bin D., 2003, *Anal Lett.* Vol.36, pp. 627.
 17. Reddy V.K., Chenniaiah A., Reddy P.R., Reddy T.S., 2003, *Chem Anal.*, 2003, Vol.48, 733.
 18. Naik R.M., Tiwari R.K., Singh P.K., Yadav S.B.S., 2007, *Int J Chem Kinet.*, 2007, Vol.39, 447.
 19. Naik R.M., Sarkar J, Chaturvedi D.D., 2005, *Int J Chem Kinet.*, Vol.37, pp.22.
- Naik R.M., Tiwari R.K., Singh P.K., Tiwari A., Prasad S., 2005, *Trans Met chem.*, Vol.30, pp.968.

20. Foretic B., Burger N., Hankonyi V.,1995, *Polyhedron.*, Vol.14,pp. 605.
21. Job P.,1928, *Ann Chem.*, Vol. 9,pp. 133
22. Williard M.H., Merritt (Jr.) L.L., Dean J.A., 1977,*Instrumental Methods of Analysis*;New York: Litton Edu. Pub Inc,pp. 121.
23. Weast R.C.,1969, *CRC Handbook of chemistry and Physics*, Ohio: The chemical Rubber Co. 49th edn., pp.D.79.
24. Sousa J.R., Dogcnes I., C.N.; Carvalho I.M.M., Temperini M.I., Tanaka A.A., Moreira I.S.,2003, *Dalton Trans.*, Vol.11,pp.2231.